

Cellular-Satellite Multi-Connectivity with Link Activation based on Random Forest Classifier

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Abstract—In the context of the Horizon Europe COMMECT project, we seek to develop a multi-connectivity solution that intelligently integrates cellular and satellite networks for the purpose of monitoring livestock transport in rural regions, where 5G coverage is limited. To achieve seamless connection in the multi-connectivity solution, we use machine learning (ML) based on a Random Forest (RF) classifier to efficiently integrate 5G and satellite links. The binary output of the classifier is used to activate the satellite link, in addition to the cellular link, to ensure uninterrupted connection according to the targeted performance criteria, often necessary in rural areas with limited 5G coverage. The input to the ML model are radio-related key performance indicators (KPIs). In our emulation, using experimental data, we demonstrate that our proposed solution fulfills the seamless connectivity requirements of the COMMECT project in most cases through the combined utilization of cellular networks and satellite links. This is achievable because the RF classifier, based on pre-processed radio KPIs, can accurately predict when the cellular network is unable to provide satisfactory service with a success rate of 94.3%. The proposed solution achieves the level of application throughput required to support monitoring of livestock transport, thereby advancing communication systems for various scenarios of limited 5G connectivity.

Index Terms—5G, Satellite network, Link Emulation, Multi-connectivity, Machine Learning

I. INTRODUCTION

Variations in cellular connectivity and accompanying network performance exist notably across distinct geographic areas and generations of mobile technologies. According to a report from 2023 [1], 5G networks have achieved a coverage rate of approximately 40% of the global population. The limited connectivity of terrestrial networks (TN) in rural areas, particularly for 5G technology, presents challenges for numerous developments and applications, such as distance learning, telemedicine, and emergency response systems that heavily rely on robust network connections. Ensuring high availability of connectivity may enable individuals living in remote locations to access crucial services and participate in digital economies, thereby promoting inclusive growth and bridging the digital divide.

This paper is based on work conducted in context of the Horizon Europe project COMMECT. One of the living labs in COMMECT has the objective to ensure the successful implementation of livestock transport systems in rural regions with limited 5G coverage. In uplink, location and sensor

information needs to be transmitted to the transport center every 15 minutes. With an estimated packet size of 5 KBytes, an uplink throughput of 16 kbps is sufficient to satisfy both current and future data requirements. In downlink, the system should support applications that calculate optimal routes based on traffic conditions, risk areas, and weather forecasts. This requires downloading up to 5 MB of content within 3-5 seconds, which necessitates a downlink throughput of 8-15 Mbps. Lastly, to guarantee uninterrupted service and reliable connectivity for seamless livestock transport applications, the system should ensure 99.9% uptime, providing the necessary throughput along the entire route. The use of multi-connectivity can be a potential solution to provide seamless internet connectivity for motoring livestock in rural areas. This technique involves the simultaneous utilization of different communication technologies to improve the overall performance. Specifically, although Non-Terrestrial Network (NTN) connections generally come at a higher cost compared to cellular network connections, they can serve as an effective supplementary link to provide seamless connectivity in areas with inadequate 5G coverage. The authors of [2] established a system architecture that would facilitate the seamless integration of cellular and satellite networks for broadband services. Despite technological and regulatory limitations, the research shows promise in delivering next-generation connectivity solutions for various vertical markets. In [3], a multi-connectivity platform was introduced that goes beyond the capabilities of current 5G networks. This platform brings together NTNs, including satellites and unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs), with terrestrial 5G and Internet of Things (IoT) networks to increase coverage and capacity while reducing operational expenses. Furthermore, to address the challenges of reliable communication in remote piloting applications for aerial vehicles, the authors of [4] suggested a multi-connectivity solution that utilized both cellular and Low-Earth Orbit (LEO) satellite networks. This approach aimed to ensure robust multi-path communication. The researchers evaluated various transport layer configurations and assessed multi-path communication through the use of different congestion control and scheduler algorithms. With the similar objective of provide the seamless connectivity in rural area, the authors in [5] proposed a dynamic packet duplication scheme for multi-connectivity

solution. The proposed scheme facilitates NTN connectivity through hybrid automatic repeat request feedback. A system level simulation has been performed to evaluate the proposed solution.

For COMECT, most relevant use cases are latency-insensitive tasks and hence suggests maximizing throughput over minimizing latency. For example, ensuring effective livestock transportation involves taking into account factors like current traffic conditions, hazardous regions, and weather predictions, which all necessitate a minimum throughput rather than low latency. From the cellular throughput measurements that will be described later, analysis shows that there is no clear correlation between throughput and radio-related KPIs (including Reference Signal Received Power (RSRP), Reference Signal Received Quality (RSRQ), and Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR)) over time. Consequently, it is challenging to trigger, or activate, multi-connectivity based on a specific KPI condition, although theoretically there should be a relationship between them. Part of the problem is the KPI measurements themselves and how they are related to data throughput, c.f. Section II-A. Recognizing the complexities of this relationship, we set out to explore the use of Machine Learning (ML) and propose a Random Forest (RF) based algorithm that utilizes radio KPIs to predict 5G link throughput to enable the efficient and smart utilization of NTN links. A few studies have explored the potential of similar algorithm, e.g., based on the Decision Tree algorithm, for predicting cellular throughput, and the above mentioned KPIs as input [6]. The multi-connectivity algorithm minimizes the cost compared to operating the NTN link alone and may potentially lead to enhanced Quality-of-Experience (QoE) for the targeted application. The following are the contributions of the paper:

- A measurement analysis of radio- and network-related KPIs
- Proposal and analysis of a Random Forest based algorithm that integrates 5G and satellite links to meet a minimum application throughput, operating on standard radio KPIs.
- Performance evaluation of the proposed solution using a hybrid emulation approach, which besides using measured cellular data, combines the openSAND satellite link emulator and the Traffic Control Network Emulator (tcnetem) for cellular link emulation.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: The details of the proposed ML model are presented in Section II, including details of the measured cellular data. Section III provides details of the emulation framework. Section IV discusses the results and the significance of the proposed solution. Finally, Section V concludes the paper with potential future directions.

II. PROPOSED ML FRAMEWORK

In this section, we discuss an outline of the proposed algorithm for the efficient utilization of NTN links in multi-connectivity. The overall framework depicted in Fig. 1 consists

Fig. 1: Overall framework for satellite/cellular multi-connectivity.

of a 5G modem that measures and provides the radio-related KPIs. The measured KPIs are then pre-processed and fed into a RF Binary Classifier, which together form the proposed algorithm. The classifier evaluates the data and classifies them into two categories: *Class 0* represents the situation in which the cellular link fails to meet the requirements of the application, and the satellite link needs to be activated; *Class 1* indicates that the cellular link satisfies the application requirements, and the system continues to use the cellular link with the satellite link deactivated. We now provide a summary of the dataset used as input for the classifier, and for the training of the ML model. Next, we delve into the data preprocessing and classification criteria that have been employed. Finally, we discuss the model training and testing processes.

A. KPI input data

The proposed algorithm employs 5G link KPIs to predict when the 5G link fails to satisfy application throughput criteria. Here, we use data from a measurement campaign which was carried out in the north part of Denmark [7]. The campaign involved evaluating both cellular and the Starlink LEO satellite network using commercially available modems. For the cellular network, a SIMCOM SIM8202G-M2 5G modem was connected to a public 5G network, and the LEO satellite connectivity was achieved using a residential Starlink terminal in clear sky conditions; the two modems were mounted on a car driving at low speed of 15 km/h to avoid the connection drop in the rural area. The data collection was conducted at different times throughout the day and on various days of the week to capture data under different network conditions. Ping and iperf tests were carried out to gather the round-trip time (RTT) and throughput, respectively, at one second intervals. Simultaneously, RSSI, RSRQ and SNR KPIs were collected from the cellular modem at a rate of one measurement per second. More details about the measurement campaign is given in [7]. Here we use the LEO satellite measurements only for performance evaluation.

From the cellular throughput measurements, we observed that there is no clear relation between throughput and the KPIs. Fig. 2 illustrates the correlation between the KPIs and 5G downlink throughput over time. To better capture

Fig. 2: Downlink throughput wrt. the radio KPIs.

the underlying trends in the data, a moving average filter with a window size of one minute was applied to the raw measurement data. It is evident that during certain periods, for instance 2000-2500 seconds, the throughput demonstrated notable improvements, aligned with favorable conditions across the three KPIs. Conversely, there are also several instances in which the throughput remains exceptionally high, despite low values of the KPIs. One such example, in particular, can be observed between 1000-1500 seconds, where the throughput remains high, at the requested rate, despite the KPIs are considerably different and lower than in the previously mentioned period. From analysis of the full dataset of 4260 seconds, we see correlation coefficient values below 0.3 between the throughput and the individual KPIs. The potential reasons may be due to the fact that the KPIs are measured based on reference signals rather than data (carrying) signals, which can introduce discrepancies. The measurements may also be impacted by applied measurement and averaging techniques in the modem firmware; often, in practise, it is not possible to know these specifics for commercially available radio modems. Furthermore, there may be several confounding variables, such as the cell load, which impacts the relation between the KPIs and the throughput. It is therefore difficult to directly identify a specific KPI condition to trigger the activation of multi-connectivity. Knowing that there should be some relation we started analysing the use of different ML models to predict the 5G link throughput based on the radio KPIs, and ended up with the solution proposed in Fig. 1.

B. Data Preprocessing and Classification Criteria

To remove short-term fluctuations in the KPIs, due to the above mentioned reasons, and highlight slightly longer-term trends in the data, we applied a moving average filter with a window size of one minute (equivalent to 60 samples); this comprises the preprocessing in Fig. 1. This also helps to better align with the throughput measurements in the subsequent ML training and performance evaluation sessions, where a similar one minute moving average filter was applied to the

throughput: since the throughput is measured at a higher protocol layer, independent from the radio KPIs, it is subject to fluctuations due to buffering at lower levels of the network protocol stack, compromising the reliability of the throughput data for analysis. Based on the COMECT requirements, we have established a throughput criterion of 25 Mbps for downlink transmission. We have established the threshold approximately 10 Mbps higher than the COMECT requirement to enable us to identify connectivity issues early on. By taking this proactive measure, we can address potential challenges before they occur, reducing the likelihood of disruptions and ensuring the uninterrupted operation in the livestock transport application. We then aim to categorize the data into two classes for binary classification. The first class, *Class 0*, comprises data points where the throughput falls below 25 Mbps, as well as their corresponding KPIs. The second class, *Class 1*, consists of the remaining dataset where throughput surpasses the specified threshold. Our objective is to accurately predict *Class 0* to consistently meet application requirements and guarantee reliable connectivity.

C. ML Model Training and Testing

The RF classifier, implemented in Python, is a form of ensemble learning that constructs a multitude of decision trees during the training process and it is employed to predict the *Class 0*. RF determines the classification by identifying the most common class label among the predictions made by the individual decision trees in the forest. This method enhances the accuracy and robustness of predictions by reducing the likelihood of overfitting, which can occur with single decision trees. Multiple decision trees are created using distinct subsets of the training data and features randomly, which promotes diversity and contributes to enhance the model performance. The configuration of the RF classifier implemented in this study sets the number of estimators ($n_estimators$) to 100, the maximum number of features to be considered for each split to the square root of the total number of features ($max_features=auto$), and allows the trees to expand until all leaves contain less than the minimum number of samples required for splitting without imposing any constraints on depth ($max_depth=None$).

We divided the original measurement data into two subsets: 70% for training and 30% for testing. We found that *Class 0* and *Class 1* had a highly unbalanced distribution, which could result in biased conclusions and skewed performance evaluations of the model. This imbalance poses challenges in accurately assessing the classifier's effectiveness, especially in differentiating between the minority and majority classes. To ensure a fair and reliable evaluation of the classifier's performance across both classes, it is essential to address this class imbalance. Therefore we employed the adaptive synthetic (ADASYN) algorithm, ML technique that uses oversampling to balance the distribution of classes in imbalanced datasets [8]. This is achieved by generating synthetic data points for

TABLE I: Classification report for mixed and original test data.

	Mixed Test Data			Original Test Data		
	Precision	Recall	f1-score	Precision	Recall	f1-score
<i>Class 0</i>	0.99	1.00	0.99	0.83	0.96	0.89
<i>Class 1</i>	1.00	0.99	0.99	1.00	0.99	0.99
Accuracy			0.99			0.99
Macro Avg	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.92	0.98	0.94
Weighted Avg	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.99

the minority class based on its density distribution, with the goal of reducing bias and improving the performance of the classifier. The ADASYN algorithm is designed to be adaptive, allowing it to adjust its approach based on the characteristics of the dataset it is being used on. We generated synthetic data using ADASYN on the training set, which was then combined with the original training data to create a mixed dataset. This mixed dataset was subsequently divided into 70% for mixed training and 30% for mixed testing. We trained the RF classifier using the mixed training set, ensuring that the model was exposed to a diverse range of scenarios. A flow diagram of the ML training is illustrated on the left in Fig. 3. To evaluate the model’s performance, we tested it on both the mixed and original test data, and their classification reports are shown in Table I. Precision is the ratio of true positive predictions made by the model to all the positive predictions made. The mixed test data yielded precision scores of 0.99 for *Class 0* and 1.00 for *Class 1*, while the original test data produced prediction scores of 0.83 for *Class 0* and 1.00 for *Class 1*, indicating more false positives for *Class 0* compared to the mixed test data. Furthermore, Recall, often referred to as sensitivity, assesses the proportion of true-positive predictions among all actual positive instances in the dataset. A recall score of 1.00 and 0.99 for *Class 0* and *Class 1* in the mixed

test data signifies that the model effectively recognizes nearly all positive cases in the dataset; while the recall for *Class 0* drops to 0.96 with the original test data, indicating the model wrongly predicted some positive instances of *Class 0*. The F1-score represents the harmonic mean of accuracy and recall. It offers a single statistic that balances accuracy and recall. The F1-score for *Class 0* is 1.0 and 0.96 in mixed and original test data, respectively. Although *Class 0* performance slightly dropped in the original test data, the model’s overall accuracy remained high at 0.99 for both test datasets, proving its robustness and reliability in the classification task.

III. HYBRID NETWORK EMULATOR

After evaluating and assessing the ML model, it is integrated into the hybrid emulator configuration as depicted on right in Fig. 3. In this setup, the trained ML model monitors the cellular link’s KPIs and makes decisions regarding whether to activate or deactivate the satellite connection based on the *Class 0* classification. These decisions are then passed to the *multi-connectivity tool* that enables and disables the satellite link connection. One such example of *multi-connectivity tool* can be a multi-connectivity tunneling program, developed at Aalborg University [9]. The major component of the emulator setup are following:

A. Satellite Emulator

The openSAND emulator is an open-source platform utilized to replicate the DVB-RCS2 (Digital Video Broadcasting - Return Channel Satellite) and DVB-S2 (Digital Video Broadcasting - Satellite) standards for satellite communication [10]. It offers researchers the opportunity to test, develop, and demonstrate cutting-edge satellite network technologies.

Fig. 3: Training and evaluation of ML model in hybrid network emulator.

Fig. 4: CDF of emulation and measurement data, (a) Throughput, (b) RTT.

TABLE II: Statistics of 5G link measured and emulated data.

		Mean	Median	Std. Dev.
Throughput	Measured (Mbps)	78.3	98.0	35.9
	Emulated (Mbps)	79.3	92.5	28.4
RTT	Measured (ms)	108.6	28.8	264.4
	Emulated (ms)	77.8	30.6	202.7

In our study, we used the openSAND emulator to emulate the satellite link. We configured the openSAND emulator to achieve a minimum throughput of 25 Mbps as per COMMECT project requirement.

B. Cellular Emulator

We employed the Traffic Control Network Emulator (tc-netem) [11], a Linux-based utility, to emulate the cellular 5G link. This tool is designed to test protocols by replicating the characteristics of real-world networks, and it can introduce a range of network impairments, including delay, loss, duplication, and packet corruption. By incorporating measured RTT and throughput data from our conducted 5G measurement campaign, we emulate a realistic cellular link in real-time. Fig.4(a) and 4(b) show the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the measured and emulated data for throughput and RTT, respectively, demonstrating how tc-netem is able to replicate the (ensemble) statistics of the measured data based on the configured network impairments.. The summary statistics of the 5G link measurement data and emulated data are shown in Table II.

Two Next generation Units of Computing (NUCs) were utilized in the hybrid emulator as shown in Fig. 3 to emulate the satellite and cellular links. NUC-2 was configured with the openSAND emulator, while NUC-1 implemented the cellular emulator that integrated with the trained ML model. To assess the efficacy of the smart multi-connectivity approach, we conducted iperf3 tests on NUC-1. Then the routing of the packets was determined by the outcome of the proposed ML model, which evaluated the radio KPIs to determine the communication link that would satisfy the targeted performance criteria. If the ML model prediction indicates that the satellite link is required, the *multi-connectivity tool* enables the satellite

link; otherwise, it remains disabled. At the other end, a server receives the incoming packets from the active link.

IV. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF MULTI-CONNECTIVITY

The performance of the proposed ML model based on RF classifier was evaluated through emulation using real-world measurements (discussed in Section II). The purpose of this evaluation was to determine the ability of the ML model to maintain seamless connectivity in the rural area scenarios. The Fig. 5 shows a selected time frame of the single connectivity via the 5G cellular link. In this figure, the throughput drops below 25 Mbps between 1500-2000, and 2500-3000, seconds, failing to meet the targeted requirements of the application. The Fig. 6 shows the cellular and satellite link throughput over the same time frame when the proposed solution is implemented. The whole emulation duration was 3600 seconds. In Fig. 6, the yellow line indicates the instances when the RF classifier correctly identifies *Class 0*, resulting in the activation of the satellite link due to insufficient cellular connectivity. It is observed that when the satellite link is activated, it achieves the desired application throughput. During evaluation, the RF binary classifier predicted *Class 0* and *Class 1* incorrectly in a few instances as shown in Fig. 6 with red and green diamond markers. In our scenarios, the incorrect prediction of *Class 0*

Fig. 5: 5G single connectivity downlink throughput.

Fig. 6: Downlink throughput for a multi-connectivity solution using the proposed ML model.

TABLE III: Statistics of single- and multi-connectivity emulation.

Connectivity	Class 0			Class 1			Fulfillment %
	Actual	Predicted	Recall	Actual	Predicted	Recall	
Single	130	0	-	3470	0	-	96.3
Multi	130	123	94.7	3470	3453	99.5	99.8

(i.e., the actual *Class 0* but predicted as *Class 1*) is more critical than the incorrect prediction of *Class 1* because *Class 0* indicates that 5G link is unable to serve, and satellite link must enable to maintain the connectivity. The model incorrectly predicted *Class 0* in 5.3% of the cases, as shown in Fig. 6 with red color diamond markers. This somewhat compromises the efficiency of the livestock transport monitoring application in sustaining a throughput level of 25 Mbps, as indicated by the dashed black line in Fig. 6. Table III presents the statistics on single- and multi-connectivity emulation. The total instances for *Class 0* and *Class 1* were 130 and 3470, respectively. For single connectivity, the livestock monitoring application met the required throughput 96.3% of the time over the entire route. The proposed RF classifier correctly identified the unavailability of the cellular connectivity 94.7% of the instances and the multi-connectivity solution fulfilled the minimum throughput application requirement 99.8% of the time by the combined utilization of cellular and satellite links. Bridging the gap for seamless connectivity is one of the most challenging issues for cellular operators to address due to coverage challenges in some rural areas. This solution demonstrates a specific use case where multi-connectivity significantly reduces the gap aiming for 100% network availability. Additional validation of the proposed emulator framework on larger datasets would be advantageous in assessing its robustness in different conditions. While single-connectivity solutions may suffice in some regions, multi-connectivity can play a crucial role in improving connectivity reliability for various applications where uninterrupted connectivity is sought. The outcomes of the emulation study support the idea that the smart integration of satellite connections with 5G, governed by a ML model, can considerably boost connectivity and data transmission rates.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE DIRECTION

The paper provided an overview of Horizon Europe COMECT project which aims to develop a multi-connectivity solution that integrates cellular and satellite networks to monitor livestock transport in rural regions with limited 5G coverage. The proposed solution involves using a ML model based on RF classifier to dynamically and optimally select the satellite link when the cellular link is unable to provide the necessary throughput. The emulation setup, which utilized openSAND for satellite link and tc-netem for cellular link, was utilized to evaluate the proposed solution. The RF classifier designed to identify situations of limited 5G connectivity based on radio KPIs demonstrated an accuracy of 94.7% and it was trained using the experimental data collected

during the measurement campaign. Additionally, the multi-connectivity solution incorporating the proposed ML model achieved high levels of uninterrupted connectivity, where satellite link serve as a backup and takes over seamlessly when the cellular link experienced limited coverage and failed to meet the required application throughput of COMECT Project. This solution can be applicable to a variety of applications that face the issue of limited coverage.

In future research, we plan to implement the proposed multi-connectivity solution that utilises ML model in real-world scenarios over several measurement campaigns and new target parameters, such as, latency, to improve the emulation framework. Thus, the evaluation of the proposed solution's performance in diverse network conditions enhances its reliability and adaptability, making it more appropriate for areas with limited connectivity.

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